

EFFECT OF STABILITY LOSS OF FIBERS ON STRUCTURE AND
PROPERTIES OF EXPLOSIVELY WELDED FIBER-REINFORCED
COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Recent interest in the development of new composite materials with a metal matrix has been motivated by the possibility of their usage under more complicated temperature-force loading conditions, as compared to composite materials with a polymeric matrix. The explosive welding is a universal technique for obtaining metallic materials in a solid state, which is independent of their chemical compatibility. In this connection, of special interest are titanium-based materials reinforced by high-strength and high-modulus metallic fibers. The stability loss of reinforcing fibers under their dynamic loading during the explosive welding affects the structure and properties of the composite.

In this paper the phenomenon resulting in the stability loss of the reinforcement fibers and its role in the formation of structure and deformation characteristics of fiber-reinforced composite materials are under investigation.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the ultimate strength of fiber-reinforced composite materials with a metal matrix, whatever the method of their fabrication, is realized in the direction coinciding with that of fiber direction in the case of unidirectional reinforcement, resulting in the anisotropy of properties of unidirectional composites. When producing fiber-reinforced composite materials by the explosive welding, a specific buckling of initially flat metallic fibers is observed as the joining is formed. Thus, the problem occurs, which calls for determining the role of this phenomenon in formation of structure and properties of fiber-reinforced composite materials, within the model available, describing the stability loss of the reinforcement fibers under high-rate collision.

BEHAVIOUR OF REINFORCEMENT FIBERS UNDER PULSE LOADING

Explosive welding of metals represents the process of joining of metallic materials as a result of high-rate collision. With choosing appropriate geometries of explosive welding when producing fiber-reinforced composite materials, there occurs a successive collision of matrix plates and reinforcement fibers. In so doing the joining line moves with a finite velocity in the direction coinciding with that of detonation front propagation in the explosive. In the case of unidirectional fibers,

the geometries of explosive welding admit longitudinal¹ and transverse² reinforcement, in both cases the bulk content of reinforcement fibers being 20 to 25 %. A durable joining of matrix plates in the space between fibers and matrix plates with fibers themselves thereby is provided, and, as a result, the material is formed which is in accord with the definition of "fiber-reinforced composite material". When these conditions are not fulfilled, the resulting properties differ essentially from the desirable ones.

When the direction of fibers coincides with that of joining line propagation under the explosive welding, there is observed a regular bending of fibers. The study of the fiber behaviour under an intense compression within a variable interval³ of time admits interpretation of this phenomenon as the phenomenon of dynamic stability loss. The stability loss of reinforcement fibers results in a significant variation in both fiber shape and collision geometry, and, consequently, in the form of joining boundary (Fig. 1).

DEFORMATION CHARACTERISTICS OF FIBER-REINFORCED TITANIUM-BASED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

The possibility of predicting strength of a construction as a whole on the basis of the well-known properties of components and the interaction degree at the matrix-fiber interface is of particular interest, from the standpoint of creating continuous-fiber-reinforced composite materials by the explosive welding. With a sufficiently anisotropic composite structure, the properties of components and the character of their interaction are to be studied experimentally in order to reveal the peculiarities of fracture of fiber-reinforced composite materials and to construct the model of fracture under a long-term loading.

The contribution of fibers into a long-time strength of the fiber-reinforced composites is the basic one, even though the role of the matrix in the process of retarded deformation is also significant. Prior to investigation of the characteristics of composites under different temperatures and loading types, matrices and fibers were tested under the same conditions. Thereupon the change-over to studying the effect of structure, loading parameters and interaction degree of components upon creep and long-time strength of a composite becomes possible. Under nonoptimal regimes of explosive welding, an initial stage of physico-chemical interaction only is realized. It is characterized by bonding formation between matrix layers and the absence of it between fibers and a matrix. Under optimal regimes of explosive welding, the conditions of bonding formation between the components are mainly related to the bonding zones at the matrix-fiber interface. In this case the fracture mechanism under the loading applied along fibers is determined by the strength of fibers themselves.

At the same time, the fiber bending due to the stability loss must affect the properties of the composite and the character of its behaviour under the loading. Therefore, to define the explosive welding as a method of producing fiber-reinforced composite materials, it is necessary to investigate the dependence of a long-time strength of the composite on the matrix-fiber interface and the fiber stability loss effect on the composite durability as well. Fig. 2 shows the curves of creep of high strength steel fiber-reinforced titanium-based composite under $T=723^{\circ}\text{K}$ without fiber-stability loss (a) and with it (b). It is seen that the creep curves for the composite with fiber-stability loss (i) are not always classic in their form, which is characterized by the presence of three stages, and (ii) a slight variation in stress results

in a sharp change of their form and the character of deformation history. Such an instability of creep curves is associated with both the fiber-stability loss effect and composite fracture mechanics. The fiber stability loss results in noticeable changes in its form and, consequently, it is almost impossible to differentiate the proper creep of the composite due to the creep of the reinforcing fibers and the matrix from the composite deformation due to straightening of fibers. Therefore, the given curves represent both the total deformation due to straightening of the fibers and their associated stress redistribution in the fracture zone as well as the creep of fibers and matrix. The

Fig. 1.

stability loss wave length is comparable with the fracture localization zone.

Among the factors responsible for the fracture is a tendency of a reinforcing phase to a brittle fracture that also contributes to the spread of experimental data. When the stability loss does not take place, it is possible to analyze the effect of the conditions at the interface between the components on the durability and to estimate in the general form the reinforcement effect on the deformation character, creep characteristics and long-time strength of composites. To do this, on the basis of creep curves (Fig. 2) displaying the deformation history dependent on loading parameters under the explosive welding and the conditions at the interface between a matrix and fibers, the curves of long-time strength have been constructed (Fig. 3), which make it possible to reveal the three levels of the long-time strength curves for a given composite. As is seen from the comparison of the curves obtained, the fiber-stability loss is the most detrimental to the long-time strength. Eliminating the stability loss allows the level of acting stresses to be increased up to 150 to 300 MPa. The further resource of increasing the long-time strength consists in improving the connections at the fiber-matrix interface that makes it possible to increase the acting stress at the same long-time strength by 50 to 150 MPa and to achieve optimum strength properties of a composite.

Fig. 2.

The creep and long-time strength characteristics of the composite under optimum regimes of explosive welding have been used to estimate the reinforcement effect as compared to the unreinforced matrix. It has been established that the reinforcement leads to a sufficient increase in both short- and long-time strength and creep resistance.

The titanium-based composite reinforced by high-strength steel fibers stands up to a 100-hours test under $\sigma = 600$ MPa, while the specimens of unreinforced titanium could stand up to $\sigma = 40$ MPa only.

Very efficient is the reinforcement for increasing creep resistance. The value of a relative elongation at the instant of fracture of composites ranges from 5 to 7%, while for unreinforced materials it is found to be 30 to 35%. The above results are in agreement with those of fractographic analysis of the fracture surface after testing, which corroborate the effect of the conditions at the matrix-fiber interface. When the joining at this interface is insufficient, the matrix fracture zone is localized in the plane normal to the longitudinal axis of the specimen, the fibers extend far beyond the matrix boundaries, and the region of fiber discontinuities extends along the specimen axis. The optimum composite structure corresponds to the maximum bonding strength, for which the fractographic analysis makes it possible to reveal the picture of fracture, as the most typical one, when the fiber spalling planes, being at different angles to the fracture surface, as a rule, do not extend beyond this surface.

Analogous results have been obtained for the titanium-based composites reinforced by molybdenum and other fibers.

The reinforcement effect upon deformation characteristics and long-time strength under tests for different times have been listed in Table.

Table. Reinforcement effect upon deformation characteristics and long-time strength

Material	Fiber diameter, mm	T° , K	δ %	MPa		
				σ_1	σ_{10}	σ_{100}
Titanium	-	723	25-30	80	50	40
Titanium - steel fibers	0.15	723	5-7	660	630	600
Titanium - molybdenum fibers	0.8	873	12-14	140	115	100

CONCLUSION

Producing titanium-based composite materials reinforced by high-strength metal fibers by the explosive welding is efficient from the point of

Fig. 3.

view of increasing the long-time strength and durability as well as creep resistance.

A dynamic stability loss of reinforcing fibers results in a noticeable variation of the bonding formation conditions at the matrix-matrix or fiber-matrix interfaces, that affects the deformation characteristics and eliminates the possibility of their predicting.

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